

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION RESOURCES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND THE REQUIREMENTS IMPOSED ON THEM

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Abstract. *This article discusses the application of information and communication technologies in foreign language teaching and their contribution to the educational process. It analyzes the use of modern electronic educational publications, multimedia textbooks, interactive programs, and electronic testing systems to modernize education. Specifically, the role of information technologies in learning English and the potential of multimedia tools in creating a convenient and effective learning environment for students are highlighted. The article also explores the use of internet resources, methods of collecting, processing, and storing information, and their impact on enhancing the effectiveness of teaching. It examines how pedagogical technologies and information tools can improve educational outcomes.*

Keywords: *Foreign language teaching, Information technologies, Multimedia textbooks, Electronic educational publications, Interactive programs, Electronic testing systems, Internet resources, Educational process, Independent learning, Pedagogical technologies, Educational effectiveness.*

ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ И КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫЕ РЕСУРСЫ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ И ТРЕБОВАНИЯ, КОТОРЫЕ К НИМ ПРИМЕНЯЮТСЯ

Аннотация. *Данная статья рассматривает применение информационных и коммуникационных технологий в преподавании иностранных языков и их вклад в образовательный процесс. Анализируются современные электронные учебные издания, мультимедийные учебники, интерактивные программы и электронные тестовые системы для модернизации образования. Особенно акцентируется внимание на роли информационных технологий в изучении английского языка и возможностях мультимедийных инструментов для создания удобной и эффективной учебной среды для студентов. Также в статье рассматривается использование интернет-ресурсов, методы сбора, обработки и хранения информации, а также их влияние на повышение*

эффективности преподавания. Исследуется, как педагогические технологии и информационные средства могут улучшить результаты образования.

***Ключевые слова:** Преподавание иностранных языков, информационные технологии, мультимедийные учебники, электронные учебные издания, интерактивные программы, электронные тестовые системы, интернет-ресурсы, образовательный процесс, самостоятельное обучение, педагогические технологии, эффективность образования.*

In our republic, extensive work is being done to apply pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process. The scientific and theoretical foundations of this issue, as well as the unique aspects of each pedagogical technology, have been developed, and sufficient experimental data has been collected. Foreign organizations related to this field are actively assisting in the implementation of pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process. It is well known that the first focus in implementing this direction was placed on the learning of foreign languages. The use of information tools, especially in the learning of English, and the development of corresponding software programs, have yielded results in achieving the set objectives. Of course, all these are modern programs that offer a set of conveniences available for use in the educational process. An analysis of modern educational electronic publications shows that their complex structure requires classification. The classification of educational electronic publications is based on the general methods of classification for educational, electronic, and software tools.

The main form of educational process is the lecture. A lecture is a form of organizing the learning process that serves as a guiding basis for the knowledge that students need to master.

There are three main types of lectures: introductory, informational, and review lectures. Depending on the subject being studied and the didactic goals, different forms of lectures can be used, such as problem-based lectures, visual lectures, press-conference lectures, and so on. In lectures, electronic educational publications are used to enrich the presented material with video recordings, audio-visual animations, and help the lecturer demonstrate complex processes.

In organizing the study of theoretical material, the following types of electronic educational publications can be used:

- **Video Lecture:** This type of lecture is recorded using a video camera. Its advantage is that it can be replayed at any time, allowing the learner to revisit difficult sections.

• **Multimedia Lecture:** Interactive teaching programs for independent learning can be created. When using such educational resources, each student can choose a learning trajectory, optimal learning pace, and method that suit them. The use of control tools can significantly increase learning outcomes.

• **Traditional Publications:** These include electronic lecture texts, supporting handouts, and methodological guides for studying theoretical material.

Independent learning of students based on information technologies includes the use of electronic textbooks, watching video collections, listening to audiocassettes, working with computer trainers, and passing computer tests. At present, all types of knowledge control can be implemented using specially developed computer programs based on electronic educational publications. The effectiveness of using electronic educational publications in ongoing and interim control systems is particularly high. Computerized test programs not only serve as self-assessment tools for learners but also take on the function of ongoing and interim control. These test programs can either be immutable standalone programs or modifiable programs filled out by the instructor.

In the field of history education, practical training plays a crucial role. Computer simulation models and trainers serve this purpose. Using computer programs, training sessions can be organized to prepare for archaeological excavations, ethnographic material collection, the reconstruction of monuments, and working with archival documents. The computerization of archives and museums creates opportunities for modernizing archival and museum practices.

Among educational electronic tools, educational-methodological complexes hold an important place. Educational-methodological complexes contain not only theoretical material but also practical tasks, tests, applications, and others. These complexes can be presented in the form of digital and analog multimedia courses, consisting of logically connected didactic elements. A modern educational multimedia course should not only contain text-based interactive materials but also present educational materials in various forms and on different information carriers.

Multimedia courses act as a comprehensive tool, providing illustrative, informative, training, and control sections to have a complex impact on the learner. The interactive part forms the core of the educational-methodological complexes, and this part is realized only on computers.

The following components are included in such complexes:

- Electronic textbook;
- Electronic reference book;
- Training complex;

- Collections of examples and problems;
- Electronic laboratory practicals;
- Computerized test systems.

An electronic textbook is designed for independent study of theoretical material and has a hypertext structure, allowing it to work with individual learning trajectories. An electronic anthology supplements the textbook content with a collection of texts. This can include documents, literary works, and excerpts from them. The methodical instructions accompanying the texts in the anthology are essential for the student. These instructions act as a guide and help establish the connection between the texts and the learning material, assisting students in preparing for seminars and practical exercises.

An electronic reference book allows users to obtain the necessary information quickly and in a compact form. It usually consists of a list of terms, with each element being hyperactive, meaning that activating it will direct the user to a hyperlink containing the term's definition, translation, or explanation. The presence of an electronic reference book is an essential requirement for the learning management system.

Internet Resources in English Language Education

Among electronic educational publications, network resources on the Internet are becoming increasingly common. The number of language-related resources on the Internet is also growing. Gradually, databases, specialized catalogs, and search systems for language resources have emerged. Working with network-based scientific-educational resources has its peculiarities, as it requires proficiency in browser use, information search methods on the Internet, and the skills to process and store the data.

The first challenge faced by language specialists using the Internet is information search.

The next challenge is to determine whether the found resources are suitable for educational purposes. There are many unverified language-related resources that may not meet the standards set by educational authorities. During the process of studying elective courses, the issue may arise that an educational manual obtained from the Internet does not match the educational institution's curriculum.

The diversity of information available on the Internet leads to the issue of choosing appropriate software and technical tools for processing it. There are numerous formats for describing textual, graphic, and audio-video information. Some solutions to these problems are discussed below.

What to Search for?

In answering this question, an English language teacher refers to their educational plan.

The structure, presentation type, purpose, and manner of presenting the information should also be considered when determining the information characteristics.

How to Search?

To find the necessary information on the Internet, it is necessary to search for resources that contain the information. Such information can be found in search engine databases, query catalogs, and other dedicated directories. Major English-language search engines include Yahoo, Wikipedia, LinkedIn, and Google. Queries in these systems are typically expressed in the form of search terms. In practice, using several search systems is advisable, as their databases differ. Specialized historical catalogs may also contain search results, information, or scientific research resources as part of their content.

Unlike search engines, catalogs are more reliable for users, as they only contain materials selected in advance according to a specific theme.

In foreign language teaching, the role of multimedia devices is very significant. The use of visual materials and audio devices helps enhance the effectiveness of the learning process. The use of multimedia tools in teaching has been an established technology since the 20th century, and its results continue to show satisfactory outcomes.

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